

Search for Potent Anthelmintics. Part VIII : 4-Substituted-7-Coumarinyloxyacetyl Thiosemicarbazides and 7-Coumarinyloxymethyl-1,2,4-Triazoles and 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles

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A number of N^1 -(4-substituted-7-coumarinyloxyacetyl)- N^4 -aryl thiosemicarbazides, 3-(4-methyl-7-coumarinyloxymethyl)-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1, 2, 4-triazoles and 3-(substituted aminomethyl)-5-(4-methyl-7-coumarinyloxymethyl)-1, 3, 4-oxadiazolin-2-thione were prepared. Some of these compounds have been screened for anthelmintic and antibacterial properties.

RECENTLY coumarin derivatives¹ have gained considerable importance as strong anthelmintics. Several isothiocyanates², thioureas^{3,4} and derivatives of oxadiazole⁵ and triazole^{6,7} have been reported to exhibit appreciable activity against certain helminths. Moreover, compounds containing dialkylaminoalkylamino side chain⁸ have also achieved clinical utility in schistosomiasis. These varied observations induced the authors to undertake the synthesis of the title compounds with a view to asaying their anthelmintic efficacy. It was envisaged that the presence of ether linkage in them akin to that in some known anthelmintics^{9,10} might possibly increase their activity to a significant extent.

4-Substituted-7-coumarinyl oxyacetic acid hydrazide on condensation with appropriate aryl isothiocyanates in the presence of glacial acetic acid afforded the desired thiosemicarbazides. The latter were subsequently cyclised by heating with 2N-sodium hydroxide to yield the respective 1,2,4-triazoles.

Refluxing 4-methyl-7-coumarinyloxyacetic acid hydrazide with carbon disulphide in the presence of ethanolic potassium hydroxide furnished 2-mercaptol-5-(4-methyl-7-coumarinyloxymethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole. The condensation of this oxadiazole with formaldehyde and an appropriate secondary amine produced corresponding 3-substituted amino methyl derivatives.

The anthelmintic screening of some more compounds is in process and the results will be published elsewhere.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. I. R. spectra

were taken in Perkin-Elmer spectrometer in KBr pellets.

4-Methyl-7-coumarinyloxyacetic acid hydrazide and 7-coumarinyloxyacetic acid hydrazide were synthesised by the method reported by us earlier¹¹. The isothiocyanates were prepared according to a known procedure¹².

N^1 -(4-Substituted-7-coumarinyloxyacetyl)- N^4 -aryl thiosemicarbazides (I) :

Equimolar proportions of 4-substituted-7-coumarinyloxyacetic acid hydrazide and aryl isothiocyanates were dissolved in a minimum volume of glacial acetic acid and the resulting solution was refluxed for 4 hr. on a steam bath. The reaction mixture was then concentrated under reduced pressure and cooled. The solid which separated out was filtered, washed with a little ether and recrystallised from acetic acid, acetic acid-ethanol mixture or dioxane.

The presence of characteristic bands for lactone C=O (1710-1720 cm^{-1}), amide C=O (1630-1640 cm^{-1}), NH-(3100-3200 cm^{-1}) Ar-O-CH₃ (1120-1140 cm^{-1}) and C=S (1220-1240 cm^{-1}) groups in the infra red spectra of above thiosemicarbazides provided a convincing evidence for their structures.

The other physical characteristics and analytical data of the above compounds are given in Table I.

3-(4-Methyl-7-coumarinyloxymethyl)-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1, 2, 4-Triazoles (II) :

N^1 -(4-Methyl-7-coumarinyloxyacetyl)- N^4 -arylthiosemicarbazide (0.0025 mole) and 2N-sodium hydroxide (15 ml) were refluxed on a sand bath for 3 to 4 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and then

poured with stirring into ice cold water containing little acetic acid. The precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol or acetic acid.

I. R. spectra of the above compounds showed bands at $1710-1720\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Lactone $\text{C}=\text{O}$), $1120-1135\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\text{Ar}-\text{O}-\text{CH}_3$) and $1220-1240\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\text{C}=\text{S}$).

The triazoles thus prepared are described in Table 2.

2-Mercapto-5-(4-methyl-7-coumarinyloxymethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole :

To a mixture of 4-methyl-7-coumarinyloxycetic

acid hydrazide (12.4 g), potassium hydroxide (2.8 g), water (15 ml) and alcohol (60 ml) taken in a r. b. flask, carbon disulphide (5 ml) was added. The contents of the flask were refluxed on a steam bath for 10 hr. The solvent was then distilled off from the reaction mixture. The residue obtained was dissolved in water. The resulting solution after being filtered was poured into ice cold water containing hydrochloric acid. The precipitate formed was filtered and crystallised from acetic acid-ethanol mixture, Yield, 45%, m.p. 210° ; ν_{max} ; 3120 cm^{-1} (N-H stretching of $\text{C}-\text{NH}-$), 1710 cm^{-1} (Lactone $\text{C}=\text{O}$),

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1140 cm^{-1} ($\text{Ar}-\text{O}-\text{CH}_3$); (Found: C, 53.26; H, 3.41; N, 9.38%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{S}$: C, 53.79; H, 3.45; N, 9.66%).

TABLE—1 N^1 -(4-SUBSTITUTED (R)-7-COUMARINYOXYACETYL)- N^4 -ARYL THIOSEMICARBAZIDES

S. No.	R	Aryl	m.p. °C	Yield %	Formula	%Nitrogen	
						Found	Calcd.
1.*	CH_3	Phenyl	243	60	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{S}$	10.54	10.97
2.	CH_3	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	223	65	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{S}$	10.71	10.58
3.	CH_3	α -Naphthyl	284	55	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{S}$	9.62	9.70
4.	CH_3	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	288	66	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{SBr}$	8.86	9.09
5.*	CH_3	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	256-57	52	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{S}$	10.41	10.58
6.	CH_3	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	289	56	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{S}$	10.35	10.17
7.	CH_3	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	210	58	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{SCl}$	9.82	10.06
8.	CH_3	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	249	63	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{SCl}$	10.43	10.06
9.	CH_3	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	279	68	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{S}$	9.54	9.84
10.	H	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	230	53	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{SCl}$	10.12	10.41
11.	H	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	222	58	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{SBr}$	9.60	9.37
12.	H	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	234	60	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{S}$	10.25	10.53
13.*	H	Phenyl	256	55	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{S}$	11.33	11.38
14.	H	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	218	54	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{S}$	10.78	10.97
15.	H	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	196	50	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{S}$	11.27	10.97
16.	H	α -Naphthyl	224	56	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{S}$	10.38	10.02

*Analysed satisfactorily for sulphur.

TABLE—2 3-(4-METHYL-7-COUMARINYOXYMETHYL)-4-ARYL-5-MERCAPTO-1, 2, 4-TRIAZOLES †

S. No.	Aryl	m.p. °C	Yield %	Formula	%Nitrogen	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	Phenyl	251	48	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3\text{S}$	10.60	11.51
2.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	206	53	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3\text{S}$	11.03	11.08
3.	α -Naphthyl	249	47	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3\text{S}$	9.84	10.12
4.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	225-26	55	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3\text{SBr}$	9.65	9.46
5.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	237	51	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3\text{S}$	11.25	11.08
6.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	204	57	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_4\text{N}_3\text{S}$	10.38	10.63
7.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	238	62	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3\text{SCl}$	10.22	10.51
8.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	249	47	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3\text{SCl}$	10.19	10.51

†All the compounds were evaluated for antibacterial activity.

3-(Substituted aminomethyl)-5-(4-methyl-7-coumarinyloxymethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazolin-2-thione(III) :

2-Mercapto-5-(4-methyl-7-coumarinyloxymethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (0.0033 mol) was refluxed with aqueous formaldehyde (40%) (0.004 mol) and an appropriate secondary amine (0.0033 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) for 4 hr. Subsequent cooling and distilling off the solvent left a pasty mass. The latter was triturated with cold dilute hydrochloric acid to yield a solid which was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from D.M.F.-ethanol mixture.

The structures of the above compounds were supported by the presence of I. R. spectral bands at 1710-1720 cm^{-1} (Lactone C=O), 1220-1230 cm^{-1} (C=S), 1120-1140 cm^{-1} (Ar-O-CH₂-) and the absence of NH band.

Analysis, yield and melting points of oxadiazoles so prepared are recorded in Table 3.

agar diffusion method¹⁴. Of them, only 3-(4-methyl-7-coumarinyloxymethyl)-4-*p*-tolyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole showed little inhibition of the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis*.

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TABLE—3 3-(SUBSTITUTED AMINO-(NR'R'') methyl)-5-(4-METHYL-7-COUMARINYL OXYMETHYL-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLIN-2-THIONE

S. No.	NR'R''	m.p.°C	Yield %	Formula	% Nitrogen	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	Piperidino	176	45	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₃ S	10.69	10.85
2.	4-(<i>p</i> -Tolyl) piperazino	154-56	42	C ₂₅ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₄ S	11.46	11.72
3.‡	Morpholino	152-54	47	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₃ S	10.56	10.80
4.	Dimethylamino	122	48	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₃ S	11.12	11.20
5.	Dimethylamino	145-47	41	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₃ S	12.34	12.10
6.	Pyrrolidino	180	53	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₃ S	11.10	11.26
7.‡	4-Methylpiperazino	162-64	56	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₄ S	13.68	13.93
8.‡	4-Phenylpiperazino	148	48	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₄ S	10.23	12.07

‡Screened for anthelmintic activity.

Bioassay :

The anthelmintic activity was determined according to the method of Steward¹³.

The compounds numbered 3, 7 and 8 (Table 3) were tested in rats against *Hymenolepis nana* (representing cestodes) and *Nippostrongylus brasiliensis* (representing Nematodes) at single and three doses of 250 mg/kg body weight. However, none of these compounds exhibited significant activity.

All the compounds listed in Table 2 were also evaluated for antibacterial activity by following the

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